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Cancer in Iraq: Distribution by primary tumor site

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Abstract

Background: Little is known about the pattern of cancer in Iraq. The aim of this paper is to report the pattern of cancer in Iraq by primary tumor site in the largest series of Iraqi patients with cancer.

Patients and methods: During a five-year period (2000-2004) 63923 Iraqi patients, with various types of newly diagnosed cancer were registered by the Iraqi Ministry of Health from all Iraqi provinces with exception of 3 Northern provinces (Sulaimanyia, Erbil, and Dohouk). 32281 patients were males (50.5%) and 31652 patients were females (49.5%).

Results: Breast was by far the most common site of cancer accounted for 16% of all Iraqi patients. Lungs and the bronchi were the second most common site of cancer and the first most common site in males. Cancer in the lung and bronchus accounted for 8% of all cancers. Leukemia was the third most common cancer in Iraq accounting for 7% of all cancers. The four most commonly diagnosed types of cancer among males were cancers of the lung and bronchus, bladder, leukemia and Non-Hodgkin lymphoma (NHL), accounting for about 37.7% of estimated cancer cases in males.

The four most commonly diagnosed types of cancer among females were cancers of the breast, leukemia, uterus (including cervix and corpus) and cancers of brain and CNS, accounting for about 47.5% of estimated cancer cases in females. Breast cancer alone is accounted for % (31%) of all new cancer cases among females.

Conclusion: The pattern of cancer in Iraq by primary tumor site is rather different from the pattern in other countries like USA, Nigeria and European countries.

Keywords: Cancer-Iraq-Primary site

Introduction

Cancer is a major public health problem worldwide [1]. In 2007 cancer was the third leading cause of deaths in Iraq and the 7th leading cause of morbidity [2]. Little is known about the pattern of cancer in Iraq. The need for comprehensive knowledge about cancer forms in Iraq is mandatory to plan and establish control programs for the common cancer which may be amenable to prevention, early detection and cure. The aim of this paper is to report the pattern of cancer in Iraq by primary tumor site in the largest series of Iraq patients with cancer.

Patients an methods: During a five-year period (2000-2004) 63923 Iraqi patients, with various types of newly diagnosed cancer were registered by the Iraqi Ministry of Health from all Iraqi provinces with exception of 3 Northern provinces (Sulaimanyia, Erbil, and Dohouk). 32281 patients were males (50.5%) and 31652 patients were females (49.5%).

Results

Breast was the most common site of cancer accounted for 16% of all Iraqi patients. Lungs and the bronchi were the second most common site of cancer and the first most common site in males. Cancer in the lung and bronchus accounted for 8% of all cancers. Leukemia was the third most common cancer in Iraq accounting for 7% of all cancers. Table (1): Type of cancer by primary tumor site.

The four most commonly diagnosed types of cancer among males were cancers of the lung and bronchus, bladder, leukemia and Non-Hodgkin lymphoma , accounting for about 37.7% of estimated cancer cases in males.

The four most commonly diagnosed types of cancer among females were cancers of the breast, leukemia, uterus including cervix and corpus) and brain cancers and CNS, accounting for about 47.5% of estimated cancer cases in females. Breast cancer alone is accounted for % (31%) of all new cancer cases among females.

Figure (1) shows the 10 leading cancers by gender.

Discussion

The pattern of cancer in Iraq by primary tumor site is rather different from the pattern in other countries like USA. The

four most commonly diagnosed types of cancer among males in the USA are cancers of the prostate, lung and bronchus, colon and rectum, and bladder, accounting for about 57% % of estimated cancer cases in males[3]. The four most commonly diagnosed types of cancer among females in the USA are cancers of the breast, lung and bronchus, colon and rectum, and uterine corpus, accounting for about 56 % of estimated cancer cases in males [3].

Primary site	Total No	Male (%)	No Female (%)
Breast	10277	464(4.5%)	9813(95.5%)
Lung & bronchus	5157	4105(79.6%)	1052(20.4%)
Leukemia	4476	2618(58.5%)	1858(41.5%)
Bladder	4253	3250(76.4%)	1003(23.6%)
Brain & CNS	3871	2217(57.3%)	1654(42.7%)
NHL	3782	2283(60.4%)	1499(39.6%)
Colorectal	2736	1545(56.5%)	1191(43.5%)
Larynx	2590	1998(77%)	592(23%)
Skin excluding Melanoma	2425	1342(55.4%)	1083(44.6%)
Stomach	2108	1246(59%)	862(41%)
Uterus including Cervix and corpus)	1692	0	1692
Hodgkin disease	1502	925(61.6%)	577(38.4%)
Thyroid	1334	446(33.4%)	888(66.6%)
Kidney, pelvis& ureter	1232	754(61%)	478(39%)
Ovary	1203	0	1203
Prostate	1081	1081	0
Pancreas	1014	575(56.7%)	439(43.3%)
Bone & cartilage	999	58.7(58.8%)	412(41.2%)
Liver & bile ducts	637	358(56%)	279(44%)
Esophagus	539	342(63.5%)	197(36.5%)

Table (1): Type of cancer by primary tumor site

Male			Female	
Lung & bronchus	4105(12.7%)		Breast	9813 (31%)
Bladder	3250 (10%)		Leukemia	1858(6 %)
Leukemia	2618 (8%)		Uterus including	1692 (5.3%)
NHL	2283(7%)		Cervix and corpus)	
Brain &CNS	2217 (6.9%)		Brain &CNS	1654(5.2%)
Larynx	1998(6%)		NHL	1499(4.7%)
Colorectal	1545(4.8%)		Ovary	1203(3.8%)
Skin excluding	1342 (4%)		Colorectal	1191 (3.8%)
Melanoma			Skin excluding	1083(3.4%)
Stomach	1246(3.9%)		Melanoma	
Prostate	1081(3.3%)		Lung & bronchus	1052((3.3)
			Bladder	1003(3%)

Figure (1): The 10 leading cancers by gender.

Cancer of the lung and bronchus is the second leading cause of cancer in the USA accounting for 15% of all newly diagnosed cancer in females.

This difference is obviously attributed to the high incidence of smoking in females in the USA. Cancer of the lung and bronchus in USA females accounted for a higher percentage than Iraqi males.

Cancer of the prostate is the leading cause cancer in males in the USA accounting for 29% of the newly diagnosed cases [3]. In Iraq Cancer of the prostate is the 10th leading cause cancer in males in the USA accounting for 3.3% of the newly diagnosed cases in males only. The continued increase in the incidence of prostatic cancer has been attributed to screening with prostate-specific antigen testing [4, 5].

The most common form of cancers in Europe are breast cancer (13.5% of all cancer cases), followed by colorectal cancers (12.9%) and lung cancer (12.1%) [6].

In Nigeria cancers of the cervix (22.9%), breast (18.9%), ovary (8.2%), non-melanoma skin cancer (6.3%), and uterus (6.2%) were the most frequent female cancers. In males, cancer of the prostate (16.5%), bladder (10.2%), non-melanoma skin (9.9%), colorectal (9.3%) and connective tissue (6.3%) were most common[7]. Cancer in Africa is not only different from the cancer pattern in Iraq but also differs from the pattern observed in USA and Europe.

Conclusion: The pattern of cancer in Iraq by primary tumor site is rather different from the pattern in other countries like USA, Nigeria and European countries. This provided an important information about cancer forms in Iraq is which can be useful in planning and establishing control programs for the common cancer which can be amenable to prevention, early detection and cure.

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